

COMMUNICATIVE METHODS OF COMMUNICATION WITH STUDENTS

Khalikov A'zam Abdusalomovich

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences
Tashkent State Pedagogical University
named after Nizami

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Abstract. *One of the important factors which shows teacher's professional skill is teacher's talent of communicating with his students.*

Especially his oral effecting through word embodied in teacher's communicating talent, his talent of encountering will be basement on his achieving success on educational – upbringing activity.

In the following article different ideas relying on pedagogical experiences are given about oral effecting through word on the base of teacher's speech talent.

Keywords: *face-to-face attack, affective-communicative.*

For a teacher who systematically analyzes his teaching practice, the awareness of communicative tasks as the main instrumental component confirms how important it is, how clear the educational-influential model that carries out this becomes, the fascination, accuracy, and clarity of the impact itself.

Let's pay attention to people's everyday interactions. Imagine you have to ask a stranger something. Naturally, the main method is to ask. However, before you speak directly about what is being asked, you should strive to organize the initial situation that ensures success. In this case, you politely organize the psychological environment using known communication methods, master the object in communication, and then directly carry out the impact. Each influencing technique used in the classroom, in the process of communication with the team, must have exactly the same communicative teaching.

As a result of a survey conducted with teachers of various teaching experience, the following was revealed: many of them, despite the fact that they systematically use pedagogical influencing means, do not recognize communicative tasks as a necessary important element of the pedagogical process. In this, almost all teachers are well aware of such components as a selective system of educational methods and pedagogical influence for the systematic implementation of their pedagogical tasks.

Despite the fact that the teacher can quite successfully answer the question “What should be done in emergency situations?”, he doubts and thinks when answering the problem “How should this be done?” In order to answer this question, you need to clearly define the logic and techniques of the system of communication with students.

In the methods used in the pedagogically influencing methodology applied in the activities of A.S. Makarenko, in many cases, having precisely defined the goal in education and upbringing, one can see the establishment of the correct organization of the situation when communicating with students. In some cases, a kind of “face-to-face attack” reveals the possibility of awareness of communication, which provides the opportunity to understand what is going on even without direct communication between the teacher and the student, a system of

official conversation at meetings or joint holding of various events with the class team, which each student is capable of. Among the influential pedagogical methods used by the teacher in the educational process, especially the method of collective and individual conversation, is of great importance. However, the effectiveness of using these methods and situations that arise during communication may vary. It is these methods that ensure the effectiveness of influencing methods in the educational process.

Establishing the communicative methods used in carrying out pedagogical tasks has always been a difficult problem. Especially young teachers acutely feel these difficulties in the initial years of their activity.

The teacher's fulfillment of communicative tasks comes from different forms of pedagogical activity, the formed level of the class team, the principles of communication management, the individual age characteristics of the students who are participants in the situation. The correlation of the communicative task to the pedagogical task, the comparison of the communicative task of the chosen methodology with the educational impact and the organization of their unity ensures the process of communication and, in general, pedagogical mutual cooperation.

In this regard, the following connection can be traced: firstly, the methodology of working with the classroom team is mediated by the communication system, and secondly, the ways to solve current communicative problems of communication are determined by the strategy of the methodology of the selected pedagogical influence. A future teacher can master the basics of professional pedagogical communication in pedagogical educational institutions, during vigorous teaching activities, as well as in the process of self-education. In this case, the teacher must know in detail the following important communicative tasks:

It is considered incorrect that these areas will fully ensure the process of mastering the professional communication skills of a teacher. A systematic correlation of general creative positions with one's professional and pedagogical communication activities, determining for oneself its system, logic, and optimal individual forms are considered an inevitable condition for activities leading to the mastery of pedagogical communication. And also, the teacher must test his theoretical rules of pedagogical communication in his experiments.

How does a teacher carry out communicative tasks, and what functions does he perform in the educational process? The teacher feels well that communicative tasks have multifaceted significance in pedagogical activity. For a long time, we can continue the list of tasks that help in solving such pedagogical problems of communicative tasks as mutual cooperation with students during education and upbringing, accustoming students to perform some kind of community service, forming relationships between team members, and ensuring the necessary emotional microclimate. Teacher communicative communication is a system that has many functions:

- information and communication;
- regulatory and communicative;
- affective-communicative.

In the process of performing communicative tasks, these functions must be carried out in a complete, complex form, otherwise the effectiveness of communication between the teacher and students will decrease and will not give the intended results.

Young teachers who are just beginning their professional activities are required to acquire comprehensive, in-depth knowledge for constant self-analysis and effective pedagogical preparation for the lesson process.

In particular,

- have deep knowledge of your academic subject and thoroughly know the material being studied;
- seriously prepare for pedagogical, psychological and methodological communication with students;
- study the internal psychological characteristics of each student and class team;
- behave freely when communicating and retain your mental and psychological emotions;
- master professional skills and communication skills with a class team;
- be able to demonstrate the highest examples of pedagogical culture and pedagogical tact, develop pedagogical intelligence and worldview;
- be able to draw up a technological map of the lesson based on the criteria for choosing methods and means that correspond to the goal, objectives and content of the subjects;
- be aware of randomly occurring pedagogical situations and be able to apply drastic measures in relation to them.

The success of pedagogical training in communicating with students largely depends on the teacher's ability to master and apply communication skills and abilities.

An important component of professional pedagogical communicative communication is the teacher's ability to clearly express his thoughts and reasoning, and emotional feelings. When a teacher, in various random pedagogical situations, becomes angry, happy, offended, worried, like an actor, he must be able to find a way out from one situation to another, from one form to another.

In this sense, the famous Russian teacher A.S. Makarenko in his works expresses his thoughts about the professional qualities of a teacher as follows: “A teacher in a lesson cannot help but play a certain unique role. A teacher who does not know how to play a role on the classroom stage cannot conduct professional activities. He is, in a sense, an actor. It is completely unacceptable for our behavior, disposition, character to be a pedagogical weapon for us. We cannot allow children to be raised with the help of our emotional experiences and feelings. After all, we are people. If in other various professions it is possible to solve a problem without mental zeal, then a teacher should carry out activities without mental pain. A student sometimes has to show emotional pain in communication. To do this, the teacher must also be able to play a positive role, like an actor on stage.

However, one should not play a stage role superficially. In this game there is some kind of belt that binds the teacher with his amazing personal ability, this is a role that demonstrates your wonderful behavior. This stage play is not some dead incident or technique, but a real process that reveals hidden spiritual feelings and kindness.”

In a certain sense, a teacher in his pedagogical activity stands out for his psychological experience, unique qualities that differ from the natural feelings of representatives of other professions. It should be noted that the teacher, when performing his communicative tasks, along with representatives of other professions, lives under various influences of the external environment and in line with human feelings, and the originality of his professional activity is manifested precisely in this; the teacher’s experiences and feelings must correspond to the pedagogical goal.

In the process of a teacher performing communicative tasks, the pedagogical influences that occur due to pedagogical activity, experiences, emotions, and concerns of the teacher are the totality of complex vital and purposeful concerns of the teacher; it is in this process that the totality of vital, beyond arbitrary, concerns associated with the professional activity of the teacher is preserved. As a result, the teacher’s experience in pedagogical situations also creates a sense of responsibility towards his activities regarding pedagogical arbitrariness. Therefore, overly voluntary concerns are carried out on the basis of feelings aimed at the voluntary efforts of the teacher and pedagogical educational purposes.

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